

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF PHOTO ELECTRIC STATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Entrance: Central in Asia is located is a commune Uzbekistan long from time since grow up going energy requirements satisfy for traditional energy sources relying on is coming However , the climate change , energy safety and economic development with depends concerns increased going because of , the country now again recoverable energy sources attention is looking Again recoverable of energy different different options between the sun energy promising alternative as appear it has been . in Uzbekistan the sun light in abundance is the sun energy work release is an ideal place for Country per year average 2800-3000 hours the sun the light takes , this many Europe countries than high This comfortable climate of the government again recoverable from sources energy work release increase obligation with together photo electricity stations development for comfortable environment created in 2019 Uzbekistan government by 2030 come electricity 25 percent of its energy again recoverable from sources work release own to the front big goal by doing put it to the goal in reaching the sun energy important role plays in Uzbekistan photo electricity of stations advantages very a lot First , they in the country carbon track to reduce and climate change effect to soften big contribution addition can

Uzbekistan , the first in line , digging removable to fuel based on because of Central in Asia the most big greenhouse gases from the makers one is considered The sun to energy transition through country coal and natural to the gas has been confidence reduce carbon waste decrease and stable to development help to give can Second , the photo electricity stations traditional energy infrastructure most of the time missing long and village places energy entry provide can The sun energy local level work release it is possible long to distances energy transmission the need reduces and energy safety increases . From this besides , photoelectric stations economic to grow encourage and in Uzbekistan new work places to create can The sun electricity stations to build and technical service show qualified worker It requires strength while again

recoverable energy in the field work with to provide take coming can From this besides , photo electricity stations development foreign investments attraction to do and the sun panels and another equipment work release such as local the industry development can

World Bank information according to Uzbekistan again recoverable energy sector by 2025 2.5 billion dollars investments attraction to do opportunity have To privileges despite , in Uzbekistan photoelectric stations development with depends there are also problems . Main from problems one this investors for obstacle to be possible has been the sun electricity stations high expenses . However , years during the sun of energy price significant level down , him traditional energy sources with competitive did Another one difficulty-edge in the regions infrastructure and network connection lack of it while the sun energy national to the network transmission make it difficult can This the problem solution to do for government grid infrastructure to update and grid modernization to develop investment input need in Uzbekistan photoelectric of stations potential to open for the government again recoverable energy to the field investment input encouraging wide comprehensive politics base done to increase need Tax on it benefits , nutrition tariffs and investors financial of support another forms enters From this except , the government in order put procedures simplification and the sun electricity stations development according to sure instructions to give need Uzbekistan government this about step threw , including in 2019 again recoverable energy sources development agency organize done

Summary

Summary by doing in other words , in Uzbekistan photoelectric of stations prospect there is is a country Central in Asia again recoverable energy in the field leader to be opportunity have Photoelectric stations advantages , including carbon waste reduce , energy safety provide and economic to grow encourage important important have With that together , solution to be done need has been There are also problems , including high expenses and of infrastructure lack of such as . This difficulties eliminate reach for the government again recoverable energy to the field investments encouraging wide comprehensive politics system done to increase need Photoelectric of stations potential to open through Uzbekistan traditional energy sources has been confidence decrease , stable to development help and own citizens shiny the future provide can

Recommendations :

1. Uzbekistan government again recoverable energy in the field to investors tax benefits , nutrition tariffs and financial of help another forms such as benefits present reach need
2. Government the sun energy national to the network transmission provide for network infrastructure update and network modernization to do to develop investment input need
3. In order put procedures simplification and the sun electricity stations development according to sure instructions to give for wide comprehensive politics system done increase need
4. Government the sun energy and again recoverable of energy advantages about public , small and medium enterprises and big industry networks between awareness to increase need
5. The sun electricity stations development , knowledge and experience exchange to the experience have has been countries with international cooperation and partnership connections strengthening need

Used literature list:

1. Marat Karatayev , Michelle L. Clark (2016) in Kazakhstan there is energy systems and green energy potential seeing exit
2. Golara Ghasemi, Younes Noorollahi , Hamed Alavi, Mousa Marzband , Mahmoud Shahbazi (2019) Sun in Iran energy work release theoretical and technical potential evaluation .
3. Dirk Johan Van Vuuren, Annelizé Marnewick, Jean-Harm Pretorius (2018) Trade retail trade centers for the sun photovoltaic electricity work release theoretical in advance evaluation .
4. Abdullahi Abubakar Mas'ud, Asan Vernewy Virba, Firdaws Muhammad-Sukki , , Siti Hawa Abu-Bakar, Abu Bakar Munir, Nurul Aini Bani (2016) Sahrai of Kabir selected in countries the sun in photoelec achieved last to achievements comment Africa.
5. Dumitru Cristian, Gligor Adrian (2010) Illumination systems for again recoverable energy laboratory

